

On the Smarandache LCM dual function

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$ is defined as the greatest positive integer k such that $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ divides n . The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the calculating problem of a Dirichlet series involving the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$ and the mean value distribution property of $SL^*(n)$, obtain an exact calculating formula and a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords Smarandache LCM dual function, Dirichlet series, exact calculating formula, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of all positive integers from 1 to k . That is,

$$SL(n) = \min\{k : k \in N, n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]\}.$$

About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, many people had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see references [1] and [2]. For example, Murthy [1] proved that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, m \in N\}$ be the F.Smarandache function. Simultaneously, Murthy [1] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n? \tag{1}$$

Le Maohua [2] solved this problem completely, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}, i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Zhongtian Lv [3] proved that for any real number $x > 1$ and fixed positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now, we define the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$ as follows:

$$SL^*(n) = \max\{k : k \in N, [1, 2, \dots, k] \mid n\}.$$

For example: $SL^*(1) = 1$, $SL^*(2) = 2$, $SL^*(3) = 1$, $SL^*(4) = 2$, $SL^*(5) = 1$, $SL^*(6) = 3$, $SL^*(7) = 1$, $SL^*(8) = 2$, $SL^*(9) = 1$, $SL^*(10) = 2, \dots$. Obviously, if n is an odd number, then $SL^*(n) = 1$. If n is an even number, then $SL^*(n) \geq 2$. About the other elementary properties of $SL^*(n)$, it seems that none had studied it yet, at least we have not seen such a paper before. In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the calculating problem of the Dirichlet series:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{SL^*(n)}{n^s}, \quad (2)$$

and give an exact calculating formula for (2). At the same time, we also study the mean value properties of $SL^*(n)$, and give a sharper mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following two conclusions:

Theorem 1. For any real number $s > 1$, the series (2) is absolutely convergent, and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{SL^*(n)}{n^s} = \zeta(s) \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p^s - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]^s},$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, \sum_p denotes the summation over all primes.

Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL^*(n) = c \cdot x + O(\ln^2 x),$$

where $c = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]}$ is a constant.

Note that $\zeta(2) = \pi^2/6$, from Theorem 1 we may immediately deduce the identity:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{SL^*(n)}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p^2 - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]^2}.$$

§2. Some useful lemmas

To complete the proofs of the theorems, we need the following lemmas.

Lemma 1. For any positive integer n , there exist a prime p and a positive integer α such that

$$SL^*(n) = p^\alpha - 1.$$

Proof. Assume that $SL^*(n) = k$. From the definition of the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$ we have

$$[1, 2, \dots, k] \mid n, \quad (k+1) \nmid n,$$

else $[1, 2, \dots, k, k + 1] \mid n$, then $SL^*(n) \geq k + 1$. This contradicts with $SL^*(n) = k$. Assume that $k + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$, where p_i is a prime, $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_s$, $\alpha_i \geq 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, s$. If $s > 1$, then $p_1^{\alpha_1} \leq k$, $p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \leq k$, so

$$p_1^{\alpha_1} \mid [1, 2, \dots, k], \quad p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \mid [1, 2, \dots, k].$$

Since $(p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}) = 1$, we have

$$p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \mid [1, 2, \dots, k].$$

Namely, $k + 1 \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$. From this we deduce that $k + 1 \mid n$. This contradicts with $SL^*(n) = k$. Hence $s = 1$. Consequently $k + 1 = p^\alpha$. That is, $SL^*(n) = p^\alpha - 1$. This completes the proof of Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. Let $L(n)$ denotes the least common multiple of all positive integers from 1 to n , then we have

$$\ln(L(n)) = n + O\left(n \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-c(\ln n)^{\frac{3}{5}}}{(\ln \ln n)^{\frac{1}{5}}}\right)\right),$$

where c is a positive constant.

Proof. See reference[4].

§3. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorems. First we prove Theorem 1.

From the definition of the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$ we know that if $[1, 2, \dots, k] \mid n$, then $[1, 2, \dots, k] \leq n$, $\ln([1, 2, \dots, k]) \leq \ln n$. Hence, from Lemma 2 we have $SL^*(n) = k \leq \ln n$, $\frac{SL^*(n)}{n^s} \leq \frac{\ln n}{n^s}$. Consequently, if $s > 1$, then the Dirichlet series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{SL^*(n)}{n^s}$ is absolutely convergent. From Lemma 1 we know that $SL^*(n) = p^\alpha - 1$, then $[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1] \mid n$. Let $n = [1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1] \cdot m$, then $p \nmid m$, so for any real number $s > 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{SL^*(n)}{n^s} &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ SL^*(n)=p^\alpha-1}}^{\infty} \frac{p^\alpha - 1}{n^s} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ p \nmid m}}^{\infty} \frac{p^\alpha - 1}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1]^s \cdot m^s} \\ &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{p^\alpha - 1}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1]^s} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ p \nmid m}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s} \\ &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{p^\alpha - 1}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1]^s} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s} - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^s \cdot m^s} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{p^\alpha - 1}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1]^s} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \right) \\ &= \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s} \right) \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p^s - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]^s} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \zeta(s) \cdot \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p^s - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]^s}.$$

This proves the theorem 1.

From the definition of the Smarandache LCM dual function $SL^*(n)$, Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 we also have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} SL^*(n) &= \sum_{\substack{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}] \cdot m \leq x \\ (m, p) = 1}} (p^\alpha - 1) = \sum_{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}] \leq x} (p^\alpha - 1) \sum_{\substack{m \leq \frac{x}{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}]} \\ p \nmid m}} 1 \\ &= \sum_{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}] \leq x} (p^\alpha - 1) \left(\frac{x}{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}]} - \frac{x}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]} + O(1) \right) \\ &= x \cdot \sum_{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}] \leq x} \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]} + O \left(\sum_{[1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}] \leq x} p^\alpha \right) \\ &= x \cdot \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]} + O(\ln^2 x) \\ &= c \cdot x + O(\ln^2 x), \end{aligned}$$

where $c = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \sum_p \frac{(p^\alpha - 1)(p - 1)}{[1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha]}$ is a constant.

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

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